

Motivation Factors to Influence the Decision to Choose Thai Fabric

Pisit Potjanajaruwit

Abstract—The purpose of this research was to study the motivation factors to influence the decision to choose Thai Fabric. A multiple-stage sample was utilized to collect 400 samples from working women who had diverse occupations all over Thailand. This research was a quantitative analysis and questionnaire was used a tool to collect data. Descriptive statistics used in this research included percentage, average, and standard deviation and inferential statistics included hypothesis testing of one way ANOVA.

The research findings revealed that demographic factors and social factors had an influence to the positive idea of wearing Thai fabric ($F = 5.377$, P value < 0.05). The respondents who had the age over 41 years old had a better positive idea of wearing Thai fabric than other groups. Moreover, the findings revealed that age had influenced the positive idea of wearing Thai fabric ($F = 3.918$, P value < 0.05). The respondents who had the age over 41 years old also had stronger believe that wearing Thai fabric to work and social gatherings are socially acceptable than other groups.

Keywords—Decision, Motivation, Influence, Thai Fabric.

I. INTRODUCTION

FROM the history, Thailand is one of a few countries that has been independent for over a long period of time. One important key factor that makes this country strong is the strength of Thai culture. Nowadays, Thai culture has been assimilated with world culture. There have been many changes in Thai attitude towards its own culture. For instance, most of young Thai people do not prefer to wear Thai clothes and fabrics except when they are forced by school or senior citizens at home or at work to do so. But in fact, Thai fabric is a good commodity in the world stage. Thai silk, for example, is probably the most sought-after fabric by people from all over the world, Thai silk is celebrated for its outstanding quality, unique designs and affordability. It has a beautiful array of colors, unique patterns and plies. Thai fabric actually is not expensive at all. It is one of Thailand's great bargains. Inexpensive Thai cloths are for sale at many stores on main Roads. It comes in a variety of patterns and styles that reflect the Thai cultural and its uniqueness tradition. Regrettably, the image of Thai cloths, however, in many young people in Thailand has been associated with old and senile [1]. Another connotation of the Thai silk image is an expensive cloth and very delicate in terms of maintenance. In fact, there are many kinds of Thai clothes or Thai fabrics which are generally designed for Thai people and suits for the local climate [2]. In

Pisit Potjanajaruwit is with the Faculty of Management Science, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, 10300 Thailand. (Corresponding author phone: 662 160 1490; fax: 662 160 1491; e-mail: jokenalove@gmail.com).

general marketing, the main factors influencing the purchasing behavior of consumers are the following: Physical, Identity, Lifestyle and Store Environment [3]. However, this research paper aimed to study the demographic factors which may have the influence on the decision to choose to wear rather than the decision to choose to purchase. Since it is vital to preserve the Thai culture and Thai clothes, the researcher aimed to study what could be the motivation to influence the decision to choose Thai fabric.

II. METHODOLOGY

The Objectives of This Research

1. To study if demographic factors have any influence on the decision to choose Thai fabric.
2. To study motivation factors that can have an influence on the decision to choose Thai fabric.

Research Hypotheses

Based on literature survey the following hypotheses have been derived:

1. Different age have an influence to the decision to choose Thai fabric.
2. Different income have an influence to the decision to choose Thai fabric

Research Framework

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

This research is aimed to collect data from working woman all over Thailand. The multi-stage sampling technique was used in the stage one to make certain that every segment of representative working women have a chance to be included in the sample. Then, the non-proportional stratified sampling would be used later on to get a total of 400 samples. The sample of 400 was calculated by using Taro Yamane techniques (1973) [3]. After that all the data would be

analyzed by using SPSS for windows. One way ANOVA would be used as inferential statistics.

III. FINDINGS

The majority of respondents were private company employees and the second largest group of respondents was small business owners. The majority of respondents were single with the average age of 27 years. It was found that the lowest income was 10,000 baht and the highest income was 100,000 baht. The average income was 10,944 baht which means there were only a few high income respondents. Most of them had only a few chances to go to any social events or gatherings during the year. The majority of the respondents often traveled by bus and public transportation and only one third owned a private car.

The findings revealed that age had an influence to the positive idea of asking Thai people to wear Thai fabric to a social event. ($F=4.154$, P Value < 0.05) In terms of age, it was found that the respondents between 31-40 years old had a positive idea of asking Thai people to wear Thai fabric to social event more than other groups. Age also had an influence on whether to bring celebrity with good Thai personality to wear Thai fabric. The respondent with the age of less than 30 years old believed that it is a good idea to bring teenage stars and models to wear Thai fabric.

From the findings, it was revealed that age had an influence to the idea of neatness and uniqueness of Thai fabric ($F=6.225$, P Value < 0.05). Most of respondents with the age of less than 30 years old believed that it is a good idea to have Thai fabric to make an expensive suit and formal wear for social events. Age also had an influence as to the variety of design of formal wear by using Thai fabric. The age group of 30-40 years old had believed that Thai fabric was easy to maintain and lasts a long time than any other groups.

In terms of demographic factors and social status, the findings revealed that age had an influence to the idea that wearing Thai fabric makes a person gain a prominent status in the social events or gathering. The respondents with the age more than 41 years old expressed that Thai fabric made them feel good and stood outstanding in social events. This group also believed that Thai fabric was high acceptable in social events than any other groups.

In terms of demographic factors and wearing Thai fabric behavior, the findings revealed that age was the important factor in determine to wear Thai fabric to the social events. The respondents more than 41 years old agreed that it was acceptable to wear Thai fabric in everyday business more than the other age groups.

In terms of income and the activity to promote the wearing of Thai fabric, the findings revealed that income had an influence on the idea of promoting government officials and private companies' employees to wear Thai fabric to work. The respondents with income between 10,001 -20,000 believed it was a good idea to promote the wearing Thai fabric to work more than any other income groups.

In terms of income and the variety of Thai fabric available, the findings revealed that income had an influence to the idea

of promote the variety of Thai fabric. The respondent who had income between 10,001 -20,000 has a positive idea about the quality of Thai fabric more than other income groups.

IV. DISCUSSION/SUGGESTIONS

It is important to create a trend of wearing Thai clothes and Thai fabric and make itsocially acceptable to wear Thai fabric at different occasions. The success of promoting the wearing of Thai fabric relied on the promoting of Thai government to encourage government officials to wear Thai fabric.

There should be an encouragement that shopping for Thai fabric and wearing Thai fabric as a popular pastime among Thai people from all ages, genders and cultural backgrounds. According to the proliferation of design and image in the Thai fabric, Thai consumers need to take serious consideration to wear Thai fabric to the social events.

As mentioned by Racha and Hawkins (2005), the decision to choose to purchase Thai fabric can be divided into three stages, namely pre-purchase, purchase and post-purchase [5]. Each stage is equally important and each can alter the consumer purchasing decision. To make a purchased decision, consumers may need to recognize their personal needs to use Thai fabric, read product information, decide which and where to purchase, determine whether to purchase again from the same place from the same retailer, choose the purchasing modes, reveal their satisfaction of the product quality and finally be loyal to the Thai fabric. These highlight the complications of the purchasing process and the potential impact of encouragement from government to promote wearing Thai fabric to work and to social events.

The suggestions for the marketing plan to attract more consumers to choose to purchase and wear Thai fabric are: First, the focus should be on the middle income and upper income and people with the age of 40 or more since Thai fabric is popular among these groups. Second, the encouragement to dress should come from the government officials to make it socially acceptable to wear Thai fabric to work and to social events at the same time. Moreover, the producers of Thai fabric need to promote a variety of pattern, colors, and styles and expand the target group from the middle aged and senior citizens.

V. RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Although the findings from this research are somewhat interesting and may create some to plan to promote Thai clothes and Thai fabric, there are several limitations of this research. It is important to make an improvement in the further research to provide more fruitful and representative findings. For instance, the sample may be needed to be both male and female and more factors should be questioned in the questionnaire. More samples should be asked to collect as much data as the researcher can. Then, the findings may provide much more conclusive results. Besides, other kinds of qualitative research methods such as focus group could be used such as interview the target group so as to provide findings from different perspectives. Further research could

also be done on comparisons between different generations instead of just different age group in which they are found to have significant impact on the way Thai people make the decision to choose Thai fabric.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Chusupt and S. Visutsamut, "Consumer Behavior," Bangkok: Aimpan, 2012.
- [2] S. Ponnikorn, "Thai Consumer Behavior," Bangkok: Holitic, 2010.
- [3] Lerkpollakarn and A. Khemarangsarn, "A Study of Thai Consumer Behavior Towards Fashion Clothing," International Business Program, Silpakorn University, 2007.
- [4] T. Yamane, "Statistical and Introductory Analysis," New York: Harper, 1973
- [5] Rocha and D. Hawkins, "Age, Gender, and National Factors in Fashion Consumption," Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management, Vol. 9, No. 4 2005, pp.380-390.